

Analysis of heat stress in classrooms of different school building types

Newly-built school building type: New building part des Ehrenfried- Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasiums in Dresden

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Approach and goals

Climate change is leading to higher temperatures and more frequent heat waves, which is particularly dangerous for children under the age of 12. School classes are often in classrooms for more than six hours a day, which impairs health, well-being and learning performance when heat stress is high. Since pupils can hardly influence the temperatures, they are particularly at risk. In addition, the school building stock is usually not designed for increasingly hot summers and tends to overheat anyway due to the large window areas of classrooms. The joint project KlimaKonform II therefore investigated how high the heat load is in classrooms of different school building types in Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt and Thuringia and which measures are particularly effective.

This study uses a combined approach to analyze heat stress and thermal comfort in seven schools with different building types (see diagram, step a). These include three Wilhelminian schools (1870–1918) in Plauen, Dresden and Gera; two prefabricated schools (1970–1990) in Zeitz and Dresden; a school from the post-war period (1952) in Dresden and a newly built school, also in Dresden. This makes it possible to determine which building types are particularly susceptible to extreme heat stress.

This profile reports on the results on heat stress and thermal comfort in the school building type of the new building, based on the new part of the Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden.

The analysis follows the process shown in the diagram below and consists of several steps:

- **Step A: Selection of representative school buildings**
- **Step B: Temperature measurements in classrooms.** Continuous measurement of classroom and outdoor temperatures from June to the end of September 2024 in two classrooms per school.
- **Step C : Survey of pupils and teachers on the perceived heat stress.** At the same time, pupils and their teachers in the two classrooms per school were asked how they felt about the indoor climate in summer. The survey makes it possible to record temperature-dependent well-being.
- **Step D: Effectiveness analysis of heat adaptations via thermal building simulation.** In addition, detailed 3D models of the examined classrooms were created for thermal building simulations. In this way, the effectiveness of different adaptation measures can be tested and compared.

Linking these steps (a to d) ensures that both objectively measured and subjectively perceived aspects of thermal comfort are taken into account.

This profile focuses mainly on structural-technical and behavioural adaptation to reduce heat stress in classrooms. The equally relevant school organisational measures (location of the summer holiday period, shortened lessons, switching to cooler classrooms) and schoolyard design aspects are not the subject of this profile.

Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden

a General information about the school

Description

The "Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium" is located in the city of Dresden (Saxony). The school consists of two parts. The new part of the school (completion 2019) serves as a representative example of a new school building (after 1990) with reinforced concrete walls, reinforced concrete ceilings, large triple-glazed windows with external sun protection, ventilation openings in the façade and ventilation system. This part of the school can be seen as a good example of heat adaptation and was therefore selected. The two classrooms examined are oriented to the southeast and northwest.

Source: Google Earth, 07/2024

General Information

School level	Gymnasium
Construction type	New building in reinforced concrete construction (built in 2018)
Address	Bernhardstraße 18 01069 Dresden
Status of the renovation	New building (completion year 2019)
Grade levels taken into account	6th and 9th grade

Classroom Southeast Façade (Room N207)

Window details	Floor space	67 m ²
	Orientation of the windows	South-East
	Window glazing	Triple thermal insulation glazing (built in 2018) (Total energy transmittance glazing 53 %)
	Shading	External sun protection (slats)
	Ventilation	Ventilation system in operation from 4 a.m. to 6 p.m.
	Exterior wall	22 cm reinforced concrete with 16 cm mineral wool insulation
	Interior wall	22 cm reinforced concrete
	Ceiling	Reinforced concrete ceiling with suspended acoustic ceiling

Classroom Northwest Facade (Room N236)

Window details	Floor space	67 m ²
	Orientation of the windows	North-East
	Window glazing	Triple thermal insulation glazing (built in 2018) (Total energy transmittance glazing 53 %)
	Shading	External sun protection (slats)
	Ventilation	Ventilation system in operation from 4 a.m. to 6 p.m.
	Exterior wall	22 cm reinforced concrete with 16 cm mineral wool insulation
	Interior wall	22 cm reinforced concrete
	Ceiling	Reinforced concrete ceiling with suspended acoustic ceiling

Sources: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden: New building part

b Survey on the thermal comfort of the students

General Information
 Pupils from two classrooms were surveyed on four different days about the perception of heat stress. In room 207 (south-east façade) there were pupils of the 6th grade, in room 236 (north-west façade) of the 9th grade. On the summer day (survey day 27.08.2024), 26 students took part in room 207 and room 236 27. The selected hot days differ: For room 207 it was 14.08.2024 with 27 respondents, for room 236 07.08.2024 with 26 respondents.

Source: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

The values in the pie chart show the number of responses in each class on the day of the survey.

Pie charts comparing the perceived temperature of students in both classrooms on a typical summer day (left) and on a hot day (right).

The perceived thermal well-being was worse in room 207 with a south-east orientation than in room 236 (north-west orientation) both on a hot day and on a summer day.

The reported feeling of fatigue was significantly worse in both rooms on a summer day (left) than on a hot day. In this case, causes other than room temperature are suspected to be the cause.

Circumstances during the survey

Room 207	Room 236
Ventilation through open window	Ventilation through open window
External sun protection at the bottom	External sun protection at the bottom
Cross ventilation through open door and window	Ventilation through open window
External sun protection at the bottom	External sun protection at the bottom

Conclusion

The perceived heat stress in room 207 was significantly higher than in room 236, both on a typical summer day and on a hot day. This is also reflected in the significantly worse well-being of the pupils in room 207.

Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden: New building part

c Temperature measurements and simulations in the classroom

Outdoor temperature measurement with KLIPS sensor

● Outside temperature
 ■ School operations

The outside temperature was recorded with a KLIPS temperature sensor in the street space 300 m away (Leubnitzer Str., Dresden) in the summer of 2024. The outside temperature from 5.8 to 11.9.2024 is shown here. This study period was heavily heat-laden and showed 14 hot days (maximum outside temperature above 30°C), 4 tropical nights (minimum outside temperature at night above 20°C) and 14 tropical nights (maximum outside temperature at night above 20°C) and 14 tropical nights. 15 warm nights (minimum outside temperature at night above 18°C).

Classroom interior measurements

■ School operations
 ● Temperatur im Room N207
 ● Temperature in room N236
 Outside temperature

In the period from 5.8 to 11.9.2024, both classrooms did not exceed the critical room temperature of 30°C, but almost permanently exceeded the comfort temperature of 26°C. The maximum temperature for both rooms is about 29°C, but the temperature fluctuations within one day are much stronger for room 207, which results from the south-east orientation of the room. The temperature peaks in the late afternoon for room 236 suggest that the external sun protection was not lowered at these times.

Thermal Building Simulations of the current state (Room 207)

3-dimensional model of the two classrooms in the thermal building simulation

The comparison of the simulated with the measured room temperature curve in the actual state is satisfactory using the local climate and the assumption that the sun protection was always down, the ventilation system was in operation from 4 a.m. to 6 p.m. on weekdays and the ventilation flaps in the façade remained open at night.

Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden: New building part

d Effectiveness of heat adaptation measures and recommendations

Simulations of heat adaptation measures

The bar diagram shows the overtemperature degree hours (ÜTG) for different simulation variants of both classrooms. The ÜTG indicate how many hours and how much the comfort temperature of 26°C is exceeded in the classroom. While v0 represents the reference (actual state) of the room, the other variants show the following differences:

- Sharp increase in the ÜTG, especially in the south-east oriented classroom 207, if the external sun protection is not lowered (v1a)
- Slight reduction in heat stress in solar control glazing (g = 0.20) (v2)
- The continuous operation of the ventilation system (instead of 4 a.m. to 6 p.m.) is comparatively effective in cooling the rooms through the cool outside air at night (v8).

The above-mentioned findings are also illustrated in the presentation of the temperature profile for room 207 for a teaching week in August. Without the use of external sun protection, the heat load is about 2°C higher, with peak temperatures of over 32°C. Continuous operation of the ventilation system can reduce room temperatures by a further 2°C.

Recommendations

The measurements, surveys, simulations and comparison with the classrooms of other school buildings lead to the following assessment and recommendation for reducing heat stress:

The new building of the Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden was selected as a good example of heat-adapted construction with external shading, openable façade elements for night ventilation, its solid construction and supply air supply via a central ventilation system. Compared to other school buildings, this seems to be justified. In the very hot summer of 2024, however, the temperatures in the classrooms were usually above 26°C, but almost always below 28°C, which was not the case at most other schools. A reduction in heat stress can be achieved through more intelligent management of the ventilation system. This should go into operation at night as soon as the outside temperature is significantly lower than that of many classrooms. On hot days, the ventilation system should only be in operation during school hours so as not to transport additional warm outside air into the classrooms. Together with adapted behaviour (use of sun protection, opening of windows, etc.) and school organisational measures, this should also make it possible to operate in future extreme summers.

General recommendations, derived from the comparison of the school buildings examined, can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19651356>